

Rainfall Variability and Trend Analysis in Case of Dijo River Watershed Central Rift Valley Basin of Ethiopia

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Abstract: Rainfall is the most important variable climate element that controls and regulates agricultural operations and crop production worldwide. This study sought to evaluate rainfall variability from monthly to decadal levels, as well as its trend, in the Dijo River Watershed from 1985 to 2018. Statistical tools like; mean, SD, CV, PCI and SRAI methods were used to identify the degree of rainfall variability, distribution, frequency of drought intensity and its occurrence. Mann-Kendall's and Sen.'s slope estimator statistical test was used to compute trend detection. The result of the study shows that statically significant decreasing and increasing rainfall trend at 5% and 1% level of significance during beginning of bega season. The seasonal rainfall contributions to the annual rainfall totals varied largely over the study area. The variation of PCI values ranges from uniform during kiremt season to strongly irregular distribution at bega season. The finding also revealed that the probability of negative rainfall anomalies was increased in recent years due to rapid population growth and expansion of agriculture activities in study watershed. Due to monthly, In light of the yearly and internal annual rainfall variations and trends over the study watershed, it was recommended that an adaptation strategy be adopted to mitigate the impact of climate change.

Keywords: climate change, climate variability, mann-kendall, trend.

1. Introduction

Climate change and variability are among the most significant environmental issues of the 21st century [1]. Multiple studies [2], [3], [4], and [5] indicate that climate change has multiple effects on the global population and the global environment. The effects are significantly detrimental to rain-fed agriculture [6] upon which the economies of the majority of developing nations depend; [7] with less adaptability [8-9]. Several low-income countries in the tropical and subtropical regions are vulnerable to climate change and variability, according to [10]. According to scientific evidence, anthropogenic factors are the primary causes of the current changes to the earth's surface and atmospheric composition. In the mid-18th century, at the beginning of the industrial revolution, the anthropogenic factor began to expand globally [11]. The amounts of carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide in the atmosphere have all risen dramatically over time. For example, CO₂ concentrations grew from 280 ppm in pre-industrial times to 394 ppm in 2012, a 41 percent rise linked to human activity [12]. Climate is one of the most important aspects of the planet [13].

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Temperature, rainfall, atmospheric pressure, and relative humidity are among the dominant climate elements. For example rainfall is the primary climatic factor that governs and controls agricultural operations and crop production worldwide [14]. In order to ensure the monitoring and management of drought and water resources, it is crucial to investigate the temporal and spatial distribution of precipitation, as well as its trends [15]. Ethiopia is one of the Countries in the Horn of Africa where precipitation is distributed inconsistently due to regional and global climate effects as well as uneven topography [16]. Crop yield is largely influenced to yearly and seasonal precipitation patterns [17]. Seasonal and yearly rainfall variability in Ethiopia is mostly determined as a result of atmospheric and oceanic interactions, including the inter-tropical convergence zone (ITCZ), El Nio-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), Africa Easterly Jet (AEJ), and winds from the Indian and Atlantic Oceans [18-20]. However, due to uneven topography the rainfall distribution varies significantly in a smaller geographic area.

The seasonality of precipitation varies across several regions of Ethiopia ([20]). The majority of Ethiopia receives its heaviest rainfall from June to September (kiremt), it's driest from October to January (bega), and its least rainfall from February to May (kiremt) (belg). Among these, kiremt, the principal rainy season, accounts for 50 to 80 percent of the country's yearly precipitation and is predominant in the northern and central regions [21], and responsible for 85% to 95% of the crops production in the country [22]. Despite the fact that the highlands of the central, southern, and south-western regions of the country received significant rainfall during the Belg season (October-January), the Belg season (October-January) is the driest season in most parts of the country. However, rain falls intermittently in the north-eastern portions of Ethiopia due to the formation of the red sea convergence zone, while rain falls over the southern and south-eastern sections of the country due to the southward movement of the ITCZ [23].

Recent attention has been focused on the trend analysis of precipitation since its precise prediction influences the nation's economic development and its adaptation and mitigation plan to combat climate extremes [24]. Several studies have been conducted to evaluate rainfall trends across the country in order to identify temporal and spatial variability. For example, [25], in Adami-Tulu Jido-Kombolchaworeda, Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia, [26], in Amhara region of Ethiopia agreed that there is increasing and decreasing trend point out during annual and season rainfall pattern. However, some authors conclude that rainfall trend were decline during *Belg* season in different region of Ethiopia.

In line to, [27] the study watershed is located in the central rift valley basins, Ethiopia and characterized by a typical wet sub humid and dry semi-arid. There is great variance in yearly and seasonal precipitation from one year to the next, according to research conducted in the study region [26]. The authors attempt to study the current and future trend of rainfall and its variability in the sub-watershed study. Climate related risk such as meteorological drought, agricultural drought and hydrological drought partial and full capable of causing crop failure were observed in some part of the watershed which cause for crop failure. Until now, there is no detailed investigation was carried out on trend, concentration and variation of rainfall in the study area. Therefore, comprehensive scientific studies on temporal and spatial rainfall distribution, variability, and trend detection is absent over the study area. As a result, this study bridged this gap as it assessed in detail rainfall variability and trends analysis, in the watershed, central rift valley basin of Ethiopia. Thus, the temporal and spatial characteristic of rainfall and their trend in the watershed was assessed for the period 1985-2018.

2. Materials and Methods Methodology

2.1. Description of the study area

The Dijo watershed is located in Ethiopia's central rift valley basin, on the western side of Lake Ziway/Abijata. It's roughly 65 kilometers from Ziway town and 230 kilometers from Addis Ababa in the south. The watershed covers a total area of 1426 km². It is located between 7° 28' 40" and 7° 59' 40" north latitude and 37° 51' 40" and 38° 53' 40" east longitude Figure 1. The elevation of the watershed ranges from 1620 metres above sea level at the riverbed to 3180 meters above sea level at the upper part, with slopes ranging from flat to steep 35 degrees and extremely rough topography. Among the principal land formations are moderate to high hills, dissected gullies, a highland plateau, escarpments, and deep dissected gorges [25]. From June to September, the watershed receives a lot of rain, while from February to May; it gets very little (bi-modal rainfall patterns). From June through September, the watersheds receive the most rainfall about 65% to 70% and secondly 15 to 20% receive during February to May Figure 3. The mean annual precipitation ranges from 995mm/year at the lower part to 1104.3 mm/year in the upper part of the watershed whereas; mean annual Potential Evapo-transpiration (PET) was 153.5mm/year and also the highest and lowest temperatures are 26.9 and 13.2 degrees Celsius, respectively Figure 2.

Figure 1. Location map of the study area

Figure 2. Spatial data of a) station within and around study area, b) created Thiessen Polygon area, c) IDW of the station and d) Rainfall map of the study area

Figure 3. Long term mean monthly rainfall patterns of some selected stations within & around the watershed

2.2. Methods

Daily rainfall dataset was collected from the National Meteorological Agency (NMA). In order to avoid potential problem during climatic analysis, precipitation data was designed to visual examination and outlier detection. Carefully, identification of outlier was made to obtain truly erroneous and is not natural extreme value. For a sequential set of rainfall data, Outlier tests at the top and lower limits were computed. Outliers that were higher or lower than a threshold value were screened using the Tukey fence method, which can make in homogeneity detection more difficult. The outlier test was checked using Micro-Excel, and the data array is described as equation 1.

$$\text{Outlier test} = [Q_1 - 1.5 * IQR \text{ and } Q_3 + 1.5 * IQR] \quad (1)$$

Where Q1 and Q3 represent the lowest and highest quartiles, respectively, 1.5 is standard deviations from the mean, and IQR is the inter-quartile range. The values that fall outside of the Tukey fence are regarded as outliers. In this investigation, the limit value for this outliers test was set to 1.5 * IQR.

Table 2 evaluates the maximum and range of cumulative deviations from the mean to assess the homogeneity of selected rainfall data. In this study, the homogeneity test was conducted using the Rainbow software and Equation 2 to determine the homogeneity of rainfall.

$$S_K = \sum_{i=1}^k (x_i - \bar{x}), \text{ where } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n. \quad (2)$$

Where x_i represents the records in the series x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and \bar{x} is less than the mean. Initial value $S_K=0$ and final value $S_K=n$ both equal zero. If there is no significant change in the mean, the difference between x_i and \bar{x} will oscillate around zero.

2.3. Data analysis

The standardized coefficients of Skeweness (Z_1) and kurtosis (Z_2) statistics are described by [30], is used to test the normality of annual and seasonal rainfall series in study area. The standardized coefficients of Skeweness (Z_1) and kurtosis (Z_2) can be evaluated as equation 3 and 4.

$$Z_1 = \left[\frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^3 \right) / \left(\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \right)^{3/2}}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \right)^{3/2}} \right] / (6/N)^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

$$Z_2 = \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^{\frac{4}{N}} \right) / \left(\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^{\frac{2}{N}} \right)^2 \right] / (-3(2/N)^{0.5}) \quad (4)$$

Where, \bar{X} is the long term mean of X_i value and N is the number of year in the sample. In this investigation two statically null hypotheses were made to overcome the individual temporal samples came from population with normal distributions. Therefore, if the calculated absolute value of Z_1 and Z_2 is greater than 1.96 significant deviations from normal curve is indicated at the 95% confidence level.

2.4. Statistical analysis of rainfall variability

The coefficient of variation (CV), the standardized rainfall anomaly index (SRAI), and the precipitation concentration index have been used to calculate rainfall variability in this study (PCI). CV is computed to assess the rainfall's variability in line to [31] as equation 5. A higher value of CV is the indicator of larger variability, and vice versa which is computed as:

$$CV = \left[\frac{\delta}{\mu} \right] * 100\% \quad (5)$$

Where: CV is the coefficient of variation; μ is the mean precipitation and δ is the standard deviation of rainfall. Moreover, according to, [31] CV is used to categories rainfall event variability as low, moderate, or high. CV less than 20% is less variable, CV between 20% and 30% is moderately variable, and CV greater than 30% is very variable. The precipitation concentration index (PCI) was similarly mentioned as an indicator of precipitation concentration for seasonal and annual scales. The PCI values of the study area were computed, as given by [28], and amended by [15].

$$PCI_{annual} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} P_i^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^{12} P_i)^2} * 100 \quad (6)$$

$$PCI_{seasonal} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} P_i^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^{12} P_i)^2} * 33.33\% \quad (7)$$

Where, P_i is the rainfall amount of the i^{th} month, i run from January to December. Equation 4 is for annual PCI whereas equation 5, is utilized for analysis of seasonal PCI, in our context *Kiremt* (June to September), *Belg* (February to May) and *Bega* (October to January) as described earlier. The PCI value classifications according to, [29] were described in Table 1.

Table 1. PCI range and classification	
PCI value	Significance (temporal distribution)
$PCI \leq 10$	Uniform Precipitation Distribution
$10 < PCI \leq 15$	Moderate Precipitation Distribution
$16 < PCI \leq 20$	Irregular Precipitation Distribution
$PCI > 20$	Strong Irregularity of Precipitation Distribution

Source: [35]

The standardized rainfall anomaly index can also be used to study rainfall variability (SRAI). It is mostly used to distinguish dry and wet seasons compared to the long-term mean [30] and to analyse the frequency and severity of droughts [31]. The SRAI for this study was estimated as per the equation 8 for the specified time period, Z.

$$Z = \frac{(X_i - \bar{X})}{S} \quad (8)$$

Where Z is the standardized rainfall anomaly index, X i is the annual rainfall total for a certain year, X is the mean annual rainfall over a period of observation, and S is the standard deviation of annual rainfall over a period of observation.

Table 2. Standardized rainfall anomaly index classifications

SRAI Value	Category
$Z < -1.65$	Extreme dry
$-1.28 > Z > -1.65$	Severe dry
$-0.84 > Z > -1.28$	Moderate dry
$0.99 > Z > -0.99$	Near Normal
$1.49 > Z > 1.0$	Moderately wet
$1.99 > Z > 1.5$	Very wet
$Z > 2+$	Extremely wet

Source: [32]

In this work, the non-parametric Mann-Kendall (MK) and Sen's slope estimator were employed to investigate the changes in rainfall pattern over the selected study period. However, the output may contain an inaccuracy if the data series exhibits autocorrelation. A pre-whitening operation is conducted to eliminate autocorrelation in time series. On the basis of [33 and 32], MK trend analysis methods have been widely used to climatic variability, environmental, and hydro-meteorological investigations. The MK test evaluates trends that are statistically rising or decreasing over time. Initialize the sign of the difference between successive sample series results. On the basis of $X_j - X_k$, the sign ($X_j - X_k$) is used to represent the function that resulted in the values 1, 0 or -1 when $j > k$. S, the Mann-Kendall test statistic, is computed using the procedure outlined in Equation 9.

$$S = \sum_{K=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=K+1}^N \text{sgn}(X_j - X_k) \quad (9)$$

S is any integer between $-n \frac{(n-1)}{2}$ and $n \frac{(n-1)}{2}$, where: x_j and x_k are the sequential time series values, n is the number of data in the data set, $\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k)$ is the sign function and given as equation 10:

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) = \begin{cases} 1 = \text{if } x_j - x_k > 0 \\ 0 = \text{if } x_j - x_k = 0 \\ -1 = \text{if } x_j - x_k < 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Where x_j and x_k are the sequential precipitation and temperature values in months j and K ($j > k$), respectively, and A positive value indicates an upward trend, while a negative value indicates a downward trend. Let $x_1, x_2, x \dots x_n$ represent the number of 'n' monthly point data, where x_j is the

data point at time j . If n is smaller than 10, the absolute value of S is directly compared to the theoretical distribution of S developed by Mann and Kendall in line to [31]. H_0 is rejected in favour of H_1 if the absolute value of S is equal to or greater than the stipulated value $S/2$, where $S/2$ is the smallest S for which the probability of occurrence is less than $S/2$ under the null hypothesis of no trend. A value of S that is positive implies an upward trend, whereas a negative value suggests a downward trend. If n is at least 10 the normal approximation test is used. The first variance of S was computed as equation 11.

$$VAR(S) = \frac{1}{18} [n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{q=1}^p t_q(t_q-1)(2t_q+5)] \quad (11)$$

Where, p is the number of tied groups and t_q is the number of data values in the q^{th} group. The values of S and $VAR(S)$ are used to compute the test statistic Z as equation 12.

$$z = \begin{cases} \frac{s-1}{\sqrt{VAR(S)}} & \text{if } s > 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } s = 0 \\ \frac{s-1}{\sqrt{VAR(S)}} & \text{if } s < -1 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The choice to reject or accept the null hypothesis is subsequently made based on a comparison between Z and the crucial value at the selected level of significance.

2.5. The Sen's slope estimator

To compute the true slope of an existing trend as (change per year) of precipitation time series on annual and seasonal basis, Sen's slope estimator non parametric test is used. To estimate the slope Q in equation 13 initially, calculate the slopes of all data value pairs

$$Q = \frac{y_j - y_k}{j - k} \quad \text{where } j > k \quad (13)$$

Where y_j and y_k are data value at time period of the j and k ($j > k$) respectively. If there are n values y_j in the time series data was obtained as $N = n(n-1)/2$ estimates Q_i slope. The Sen's estimator of slope is the median of these N values of Q_i . The N values of Q_i are ranked from the smallest to the largest and the Sen's estimator is given by the equation 14.

$$Q_i = (Q_{\lfloor \frac{N+1}{2} \rfloor}), \quad \text{if } N \text{ is odd}$$

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{2} (Q_{\lfloor N/2 \rfloor} + Q_{\lfloor (N+2)/2 \rfloor}), \quad \text{if } N \text{ is even} \quad (14)$$

The value of slope estimator (Q_i) can be negative, positive or Zero, which show decreasing value with time (downward trend), increasing value with time (upward trend) and data fluctuation around the mean, respectively in time series.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of annual and seasonal rainfall variability

The mean annual rainfall of the watershed from 1985 to 2018 was 842mm, with a CV and SD of 23% and 180.67mm, respectively (table 4). The watershed received the most annual rainfall in 1995-1996, with a total of 1187.9mm, which corresponds to a moderate La Nia year. In contrast, the minimum rainfall observed was 546.3mm in 2009-2010, the driest year in almost all of Ethiopia due to a moderate EL- Nino effect (Figure 4 and Table 9). The mean values found in this study are consistent with other studies in the study area [25]. On a monthly basis, the maximum rainfall was observed in August 2004 with a value of 214.01mm, which was one of the wettest months, and the minimum rainfall was zero milli metres in January 2011, which was the driest month in the study area.

Figure 4. Annual and mean annual rainfall distribution amount in the watershed from 1985 to 2018.

The highest CV was noticed during the month of December (2.7), followed by November (2.5), January (1.56), and February (1.18) table 3. Thus almost all rainfall of the watershed shows high CV was observed. In order to examine the rainfall trend temporal distribution, was employed a simple parametric linear regression and non-parametric Mann Kendall and Sen's slope estimator methods. Both methods revealed a comparable result regarding the direction of trend whereas they have certain disagreements in portraying the magnitude of rainfall trend.

On a monthly basis, January, February, April, May, July, August, and October exhibit statistically insignificant decreasing trends, but only March shows statistically significant decreasing trends with a p-value of 0.011 for the record period. In contrast, the months of June, September, November, and December exhibit a non-significant upward trend (table 3). The contributions of seasonal rainfall to the annual rainfall was significant, for example, the *Belg* February, March, April and May (FMAM) season and Kiremt season June, July, August and September (JJAS) account for the main contributions with observed percentages of 32.4% and 58.4% respectively table 3. However, the *Bega* October, November, December and January (ONDJ) season contribute only 9.2% from total annual amount. The average rainfall of *Bega*, *Belg*, and *Kiremt* rainfall noticed to have been 72.96mm, 258.67mm and 464.98mm with, CV value of 95%, 47% and 27% and SD value of 69.34mm, 120.23mm and 123.6mm.

Figure 5. Mean monthly rainfall and its trend in Diyo watershed from 1985-2018.

Months	Mean	C V	SD V	Percentage	Skewness	Kurtosis	Mk	Sen. slope	p-value
Jan	18	1.6	28.07	2.14	1.46	1.28	-0.62	0	0.598
Feb	34.6	1.2	62.3	4.11	1.82	3.92**	-1.97*	-0.791	0.353
Mar	63.4	1	62.9	7.53	1.36	2.34**	-2.20*	-2.118	0.011
Apr	82.5	0.8	65.8	9.8	0.74	-0.02	-0.43	-0.41	0.273
May	78.2	0.7	55.3	9.29	1.23	2.78	-1.04	-1.088	0.235
Jun	89.9	0.6	54.53	10.68	0.21	-0.82	1.6	1.609	0.131
Jul	158.9	0.4	65.18	18.87	0.99	0.59	-0.62	-0.775	0.131
Aug	128.7	0.4	45.95	15.29	0.48	-0.12	-1.13	-0.824	0.89
Sep	87.5	0.6	56.22	10.39	1.92	1.9	0.76	0.536	0.385
Oct	43.3	0.6	53.53	5.14	1.82	4.9	-0.68	-0.322	0.221
Nov	6.67	2.7	17.88	0.78	4.47**	2.3*	1.24	0	0.68
Dec	5.15	2.5	12.67	0.61	0.6	1.58	0.11	0	0.63
Kiremt	465	0.3	124	58.4	1.48	3.82**	0.2	0.55	0.939
Bega	72.96	1	69.34	9.2	0.79	0.23	-2.68**	-5.94	0.002

Belg	25 8.7	0. 5	12 0.2	32.4	0.64	-0.4	- 0.17	-0.23	0.40 1
Annual	84 2	0. 2	18 0.7	100	0.26	-0.5	- 2.12*	-5.26	0.90 4

*and ** indicates statistically significant at 95% and 99% confidence level.

The non-parametric seasonal rainfall trends indicate statistically significant decreasing trend on *Bega* with a p value of 0.002, but non-significant decreasing trends on *Belg* season and annual table 3. However, the non-parametric trend indicates that non-significant increments in Kiremt (JJAS) season rainfall table 3. The seasonal and annual patterns of precipitation are depicted in Figure 6, where the linear regression slope line illustrates the rate of decrease in Belg (6.0872mm/year), Bega (0.4706mm/year), and annual precipitation (4.7143mm/year). However, the slope of the regression line indicates the rate of precipitation increase throughout Kiremt season (1.8435mm/year). Similarly, statistically significant seasonal and annual increasing and decreasing trend have been observed in different regions of Ethiopia.

Figure 6. Annual and seasonal rainfall trends of the study area

3.2. Decadal rainfall variability and trends

The finding revealed that the highest mean decadal annual rainfall value was observed during the 1st decade (1985-1995) with 889.22mm while, the lowest mean value was record in 3rd decade (2007-2017) with 759.63mm table 5. 134.63mm and 180.8mm value of SD was record at 1st and 3rd decade Table 5. Moreover, the decadal mean annual rainfall was decreased from 1st decade to 3rd decade due to expansion of agriculture and rapid population growth in watershed in alarming rate.

The statistical data, both parametric and nonparametric, demonstrated a decadal oscillation in the area's rainfall trend. Due to historically high levels of Eli during this time in Ethiopia, a non-significant decreasing trend was found throughout the first ten years (1985-1995). Figure.7 shows that the second and third decades also revealed non-significant increasing trends. When compared to previous decades, the last five years have shown incredible decreasing trends. This revealed that the decreasing trend may continue into this decade, despite aggregate rainfall increasing throughout the period. Figure 8 depicts the decadal rainfall trends, with the linear regression slope line indicating the rate of decrease in rainfall during first decade from 1985-1996 (12.369mm/year), whereas on the 2nd and 3rddecade indicates increasing trend in rainfall (17.086mm/year) and (3.7631mm/year).

Table 4. Decadal rainfall pattern statistical summary from 1985 to 2018.

Decade	Minimu m	Maximu m	Mea n	Std. deviation	M K	Sen's slope	p- value
1985- 1995	688.9	1187.9	889. 27	134.63	- 0.3	-7.025	0.545
1996- 2006	661.7	1140.5	872. 85	135.15	1.0 9	11.57	0.456
2007- 2017	546.3	1177.7	759. 63	180.8	0.4 8	5.26	0.873

Figure 7. Decadal rainfall trend from 1985 to 2018

3.3. Annual, seasonal and decadal PCI variations

On an annual basis, the precipitation concentration index (PCI) estimated values range from a low of 11.49 in 1985 to a high of 24.84 in 2017; the lowest PCI value was observed in 1985. Approximately 32.35 percent of the year had PCI values within the irregular PCI distribution range (16-20). In addition, 58.82 percent of the year was defined by a PCI value within the moderate range, while 8.82 percent of the year recorded an annual PCI value within the strong range [28]. This suggests that rainfall patterns in the research area are not uniformly distributed, but have fluctuated in the watershed between moderate, irregular, and strong irregular rainfall distribution ranges. As a result of rapid population increase, large barren lands, agriculture, and settlement area expansion, as well as major shrinkage of forest, shrub, and grass lands, have resulted in rainfall unpredictability over the previous three decades. The presence of such erratic precipitation for the 34-year watershed has resulted in a heightened risk of erosion.

Table 5. The seasonal and annual rainfall PCI value

Seasons	Mean PCI	R ²	Slope(mm/year)
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JJAS (<i>Kiremt</i>)	10	0.01	0.02
FMAM (<i>Belg</i>)	13.75	0.13	0.14
ONDJ (<i>Bega</i>)	23.46	0.012	0.08
Annual	15.99	0.015	0.037

The mean annual PCI for the Bega (ONDJ) season was estimated to be 19 on a seasonal scale (strong irregularity). For the 34-year period, 55.9 percent of the years produced a PCI value greater than 20, indicating strong irregularity in precipitation concentration, 11.8 percent of the years produced a PCI value between 11 and 15 (moderate rainfall distribution), and the remaining 32.4 percent produced a PCI value between 16 and 20.

The results show that it is wide and diverse, given the watershed's vulnerability to erosion and flooding due to the weak nature of the soil, its profile, and underlying geology once exposed as a result of anthropogenic factors on the environment, such as agricultural expansion and deforestation. Rainfall was generally uniformly distributed during the Kiremt (JJAS) season, with 35.25 percent of the 34-year period having moderate rainfall distribution and 64.7 percent of these years represented by evaluated PCI value within the even rainfall distribution. According to [15], the lowest theoretical value of PCI demonstrating perfect uniformity in rainfall distribution is 8.3. Given that the PCI values are estimated to be 10, it appears that nearly the same amount of precipitation occurs in each month of the kiremt season for 64.7 percent of these years, even though none of these years has a perfectly uniform rainfall distribution. Figure.9 and Table.6.

Figure 8. Annual and seasonal PCI of rainfall in the study area and its trend

Further, the Belg (FMAM) the average annual PCI for the Belg season was computed and found strong irregularity PCI with value of 5.88%. For the 34 year period, 14.7% of the year yielded a PCI value greater than 15 and less than 21, indexing irregularity precipitation concentration, 61.76% of

the year showed PCI value greater than 10 and less than 16 indexing moderate rainfall distribution, while the remaining 17.65% yielded PCI value of the uniform rainfall distribution. According to Figure 9 the computed standardized PCI indicates an increasing trend for *bega* and annual during the study period, but decreasing trend for *Kiremt* and *Belg*, nevertheless, although statistically insignificant.

In line to Table 7, the mean PCI value of *Bega*, (ONFJ), show strong irregularity rainfall distribution, *kiremt* (JJAS) has uniform precipitation concentration, but the *Belg* (FMAM) season exhibited a moderate distribution of precipitation. Further, on annual basis the mean PCI of the study watershed showed relatively irregularly rainfall distribution with value of 15.9. Similarly, mean PCI value has been observed in the area, particularly in the Adami - Tulu Jido kombolchaworeda, the central rift valley basin of Ethiopia by [28]. The annual and seasonal PCI trends are presented in Figure 8, where the slope linear regression line reveals the rate of decreasing in rainfall during *belg* (0.14mm/year) and *kiremt* (0.02mm/year). However slope of liner regression line indicate the increments rate in rainfall during annual (0.04mm/year) and *Bega* (0.08mm/year). Similarly, statistically insignificant seasonal and annual increasing and decreasing trend have been observed in the area, particularly in the Southern Regional State of Ethiopia [25]. On the decadal scale the *belg* season from 1985-1995 PCI value was 15.9 indexing irregular precipitation distributions. However, the decadal values of the *Kiremt* season over the three consecutive decades indicate PCI value of 10.3, 10.2 and 9.8 respectively. On the same season the mean PCI value over the three decade of *kiremt* season was 10, which show uniform precipitation distribution Table 7.

Further, the decadal PCI value of *bega* (ONDJ) season of study area was 21.51, 23.8 and 24.4 consecutively over three decade with mean PCI value of 23.4, show strong irregularity of rainfall distribution. This result implies that a strong irregular rainfall distribution over the watershed during *bega* season was increased due to LULC change in alarming rate. The annual PCI for 1985-1995, 1996-2006 and 2007-2017 fall within the irregular precipitation concentration category giving average value of 15.99, 15.3 and 16.6 respectively with average mean of 15.96 Table 6. The authors, conclude that rainfall variability in different part of country is not uniformly distributed it was fluctuated due to rapid population growth, expansion of agriculture and shrinkage of forest land, these lead to rainfall variability over the past three decades[20]. Further, [26 and 34] where argued that rainfall was more variably in *belg* season than the *kiremt* season Amhara regional state and Awash River basin of central Ethiopia.

Table 6. The PCI and CV mean decadal values for annual and season

Decade	PCI				CV			
	<i>Kiremt</i> <i>t</i>	<i>Bel</i> <i>g</i>	<i>Bega</i>	<i>Annua</i> <i>l</i>	<i>Kiremt</i> <i>t</i>	<i>Belg</i>	<i>Bega</i>	<i>Annua</i> <i>l</i>
1985-1995	10.3	15.3	21.5	15.99	20	26	34	23
1996-2006	10.2	13.9	23.8	15.3	10	30.8	30	18.1
2007-2018	9.8	12	24.4	16.6	12.67	8	28.9	16.97

		13.	23.2			26.2	30.9	
Mean	10.1	7	4	15.96	14.22	6	9	19.34

The decadal value of CV during *Kiremt*(JJAS) season from 1985-1995, 1996-2006, and 2007-2017, shows value 20, 10 and 12.67, with mean CV value 14.22, indicate less CV ($10 < CV < 20$)(Table 6). Whereas, on the same decade the CV value of *belg* (FMAM) season was 26, 30.8 and 21.98, with mean value of CV 26.26 annual rainfall whereas, show moderate coefficient of variation. Also, during *bega* (ONDJ) the decadal CV value was 34, 30, and 28.96, with mean CV value of 30.99 Table 6. The mean result of CV during *bega* season in the study area revealed that highly variable means $CV > 30$. Further, on annual basis the decadal CV value of the three consecutive decades was 23, 18.1 and 16.97, with mean value of 19.44, which indicates moderate variable Table 6. The result obtained on CV was close agreed with finding in different region of Ethiopia [14]; [21].

3.4. Annual, Seasonal and Decadal Variations of SRAI

The SRAI value indicates the minimum and maximum deviation of precipitation from its long-term average. The southern, central, and southwestern parts of the country are experiencing significant growth [24]. The SRAI show a complicated relationship with the historical record of La Nina and El Nino years Table 7 In order to prepare for drought circumstances, In the past, SRAI has been used to identify unusually dry and wet periods.

Table 7. List of El Nino and La Nina strength of years

	El Niño				La Niña	
Weak – 10	Moderate –7	Strong –5	Very Strong –3	Weak - 10	Moderate –4	Strong -7
1952- 53	1951-52	1957-58	1982-83	1954- 55	1955-56	1973-74
1953- 54	1963-64	1965-66	1997-98	1964- 65	1970-71	1975-76
1958- 59	1968-69	1972-73	2015-16	1971- 72	1995-96	1988-89
1969- 70	1986-87	1987-88		1974- 75	2011-12	1998-99
1976- 77	1994-95	1991-92		1983- 84		1999-00
1977- 78	2002-03			1984- 85		2007-08
1979- 80	2009-10			2000- 01		2010-11

2004-05			2005-06		
2006-07			2008-09		
2014-15			2016-17		

Source: (<https://ggweather.com/enso/oni.htm>)

Table 8. Percentage of positive and negative SRAI decadal values for annual and seasonal rainfall in the watershed.

Decade	Annual (%)		Kiremt(%)		Belg(%)		Bega(%)	
	SRAI (+)	SRAI (-)	SAI (+)	SRAI (-)	SRAI (+)	SRAI (-)	SRAI (+)	SRAI (-)
1985-1995	50	50	30	70	40	60	30	70
1996-2006	19.2	81.8	27.2	72.8	45.5	54.5	9	91
2007-2017	75	25	50	50	58.8	41.2	75	25
Mean	47.7	52.3	35.7	64.3	48.1	51.9	38.0	62.0

Note: (+) is positive and (-) negative.

Figure 9. SRAI annual (a) and seasonal (b, c and d) during (1985 - 2018)

In this investigation shortage of rainfall observed during, 1991, 1995, 2002, 2004, 2009, 2015 and 2016, but surplus during 1989, 1994, 1996, 2010 and 2014 as compared to the long term mean due to El Niño and LaNiña effect. Nonetheless, seasonal responses to Climate forcing by ENSO has been

rather modest variable. For example, Consider the seasonal rainfall pattern in 1997-1998, a year marked by a severe El Nino, when the driest season began with the SRAI in a moderately wet state indicating a decrease of 0.43, while nearly normal to moderately deficit conditions during kiremt show a decrease of 0.38 and extreme wet conditions during the belg season showed an increase of 1.67. Further the annual SRAI during strong EL-Nino year since 1997-1998 indicates moderated dry with value of -0.803. Figure 9 also demonstrates that a negative anomaly is more prevalent during the kiremt season than in the other seasons. Nonetheless, a statistically significant decreasing tendency is evident in the region's southern portion [19]. The annual decadal variation of SRAI from 1985-1995, 1996-2006 and 2007-2017 was calculated and obtained the mean value of 47.7 and 52.3% for positive and negative anomalies table 9. Whereas, the mean decadal values of the *kiremt* season (JJAS) was 35.7 and 64.3% for positive and negative rainfall anomalies of the study area. Further, the *belg* and *bega* season mean rainfall anomalies indicates that 48.1% and 38% for positive anomalies whereas, 51.9% and 62.0 % for negative anomalies over the past three decade table 8. Inline to the result obtained, the frequency of mean negative anomalies were increased during study periods. The result indicate that the study area has experienced more dry season than wet season. The result revealed that negative rainfall anomaly was increased because of expansion of agriculture, increment of settlement, rapid population growth. This implies chance of drought occurrence was increase due to shrinkage of natural resource over study area as whole and barren land escalation, these leads significant rainfall decreasing was observed watershed. This result support with finding of, [26], [35], the authors, concluded that annual and seasonal rainfall has shown negative and positive anomalies for different part of Ethiopia; while, percentage of occurring negative anomalies was increasing due to expansion of population and depletion of natural resource.

4. Conclusion

In this study meteorological data such as monthly and annual rainfall data of the central rift valley basin of Ethiopia were used to explore of climate variability and its trends. To comprehend the monthly, seasonal, yearly, and decadal rainfall variability and trends, both parametric and nonparametric statistical tests have been performed. Over the past 34 years, the average annual rainfall in the study region has fallen by 4.71 millimetres each year. During the *belg* (FMAM) and *bega* (ONDJ) seasons, seasonal rainfall in the study region exhibited an increasing tendency for *kiremt* totals and a declining trend for *belg* (FMAM). The MK trend test revealed that yearly and *bega* season precipitation had statistically significant decreasing trends, however *belg* season precipitation does not exhibit a statistically significant decreasing trend. However, during *kiremt* (JJAS) season rainfall was of statistically not significant increasing trend. The average annual precipitation concentration index (PCI) revealed an irregular distribution of yearly rainfall, with a uniform distribution during the *kiremt* season, a moderate distribution during the *belg* season, and a severe distribution irregularity during the *bega* season. CV in the study area showed that of moderate variation in annual and *belg* season rainfall % of CV is from 20-30%, which has less variations during *Kiremt* season % of CV is less than 20% and the highest % is CV greater than 30% during *bega* season. The result of SRAI is also indicated that inter annual variability of rainfall from the year 1985 to 2018, which were found in the study area. Due to the monthly, annual, and internal annual rainfall variability and trends within the study watershed, it may be advised that an adaptation option be taken to mitigate its impact. The results of the study will be utilised to develop watershed Plans for the sustainable administration of land and water resources in the Dijo watershed.

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